

INFLUENCE OF STRESS AND EMOTIONS REGULATION ON SUICIDAL IDEATION AMONG UNDERGRADUATE STUDENTS OF UNIVERSITY OF ABUJA, NIGERIA.

Ebenezer I. Ibinola, Monday Akawu PhD and Andrew Zamani PhD

Department of Psychology, Nasarawa State University, Keffi

E-Mail: realimageprint@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

The study investigated the influence of stress, emotions regulation on suicidal ideation among (275) undergraduates students of University of Abuja, Nigeria. They consisted of 144 Male and 131 Female. The participant responded to three sets of research instrument such as The Perceived Stress Scale (PSS), Emotion Regulation Questionnaire (ERQ) and Suicidal Ideation Attributes Scale (SIDAS). Four Hypotheses were stated and tested. The study employed inferential statistics for the test of the four hypotheses postulated in the study and the result shows that stress has a significant influence on suicidal ideation ($R = .231$; $F = 14.345$, $P < .05$) among participants. Also, the results indicates a significant impact of stress ($\beta = .231$ $t = 3.787$, $p < .05$) on suicidal ideation and suggest that increased in stress leads to relatively increased in suicidal ideation. Emotion regulation difficulties has a significant influence on suicidal ideation ($R = .214$; $F = 9.401$, $P < .05$) among participants. Also, the results indicates a significant impact of emotion regulation difficulties ($\beta = .214$ $t = 3.066$, $p < .05$) on suicidal ideation among participants. Stress and emotion regulation difficulty significantly and jointly influence student's suicidal ideation ($R = .294$; $F = 12.868$, $P < .05$) thus, accounted for about 8.6% variance for suicidal ideation among participants. Also, the results indicates a significantly independent impact of stress ($\beta = .238$ $t = 3.978$, $p < .05$) and emotion regulation difficulty ($\beta = .224$ $t = 2.297$, $p < .05$) on suicidal ideation participants. The findings were discussed in line with the existing literature cited in this project research. In conclusion, on the basis of the findings, it was recommended that School authorities should encourage open conversations about stress, emotions and suicidal ideation to reduce stigma and promote help-seeking behavior

Key Words: Stress, Emotions regulation and Suicidal Ideation.

Introduction

Adolescence life is a critical phase of human development, marked by significant academic, social, and emotional challenges. The transition from adolescence to young adulthood can be overwhelming, and students often struggle to cope with the demands of university life. Stress, emotion regulation difficulties, can exacerbate these challenges, leading to severe mental health issues, including suicidal ideation.

Suicidal ideation refers to thoughts or feelings about ending one's life. These thought can range from vague ideas or fantasies to more detailed planning of how to carry out suicide. Suicidal ideation is often a symptoms of underlying emotional distress or mental health conditions, such as emotions regulation difficulties, depression, anxiety, trauma, or substance abuse.

There are generally two types of suicidal ideation:

Passive Suicidal Ideation: This involves wishing you were dead or thinking about not wanting to live but without actively planning to end your life.

Active Suicidal Ideation: This includes not only thinking about suicide but also planning or intending to take specific actions to end your life.

Suicidal ideation is a signal that someone is struggling deeply and needs support, compassion, and possibly professional help.

Stress is a ubiquitous experience among students, stemming from academic pressures, social anxiety, and financial concerns. The American College Health Association (2019) reported that 60% of students experience overwhelming anxiety, while 40% report feeling hopeless. Emotion regulation difficulties can worsen stress, as students may struggle to manage their emotions effectively.

Stress as an inescapable part of life generally touches a wide range of groups of population with no regard to their age, gender, educational status or socioeconomic status. Despite this fact, stress, emotional regulation difficulty are prevailing mental health problems among college students (Kitzrow, 2003; Marthoenis, et al., & Sofyan, et al., 2018). College students undergo numerous educational, social, environmental and psychological adjustment difficulties in the new campus atmosphere which may affect their psychosocial well-being and learning outcomes. These happen because the new tertiary educational system has a big difference in its methods of teaching, academic requirements, type of relations between faculties and even relations among students themselves (Thawabieh & Qaisy, 2012). In short, stress seems to be very common in college students' life because college students need to ensure their academic survival and prepare themselves for the further career. It is not a surprise that much of the academic stress at the college level is associated with what students learn and how they learn it.

Stress can be a healthy and adaptive, people's response to the threat by mobilizing their energy towards the stressors (Khan et al., 2015). Thus, it is important to note that a certain level of stress is essential for the students in a way that it motivates students to progress in their academic journey actively, would otherwise be inactive and uninterested creatures (Nandamuri, 2007). Many researchers have also noted that stress is not always negative. It also partakes positive motivational contribution in people's life. Take, for instance, exam stress or academic workload may motivate and strengthen a college student to successfully deal with his or her academic tasks and also enhances academic achievement and creativity (Auerbach & Gramling, 1998). However, if individuals fail to employ effective stress coping mechanisms to handle the stressful situation, their feeling of stress can persist over time and, in turn, become at a higher risk of developing severe physical and mental problems (Auerbach & Gramling, 1998).

Given the above, stressful life event is consider in this study to play a role in antisocial behaviour like drug abuse. Stressful life events, such as family conflicts, academic pressure, unemployment, and socio-economic challenges, can exacerbate vulnerability to substance abuse among youths. These events may lead individuals to seek solace or escape through substance use, perpetuating a cycle of dependence and further stress. Experiences in these contexts can produce stress that may lead to drug use (Agnew & White, 1992; Carson et al., 2009; Preston, 2006; Stogner & Gibson, 2011). Furthermore, life stress exposure has a significant effect on behavior and has been

associated with a number of clinical disorders; like anxiety (Keyes et al., 2015), depression (WHO, 2019) and substance abuse (Andersen, 2018; Sudrabaa et al., 2015; Yan et al., 2020).

Additionally, demographic characteristics, including age, gender, education, and socio-economic status, play a pivotal role in shaping patterns of substance abuse. Youths from disadvantaged backgrounds or marginalized communities may face heightened risk factors and fewer resources for coping with stressors, increasing susceptibility to substance abuse. Overall, demographic variables are associated with a variety of outcomes, including substance dependence and abuse.

Emotions regulation is a crucial life skill that impacts mental and physical well-being, quality of life, It help individuals feel better and recover more quickly from stressful experiences, and it can also impact social relationships and overall functioning.

Emotion regulation is the ability to manage and respond to emotions in a healthy and balanced way, influencing which emotions one experiences, when they are experienced, and how they are expressed. It involves conscious and unconscious processes or strategies to modify the intensity and duration of emotions.

Conscious strategies: These involve active thought processes or commitments to behaviours, like cognitive reappraisal, where you reframe a situation to change your emotional response.

Unconscious strategies: These occurs without deliberate monitoring, influencing the intensity and duration of an emotional response. The ability to regulate emotions typically improves with age and development example, rethinking a stressful situation, hiding visible signs of sadness or focusing on reasons to feel happy.

Suicidal ideation is a growing concern among students, with rates increasing in recent years (CDC, 2020). The National Alliance on Mental Illness (2020) reported that 1 in 10 students considers suicide, highlighting the need for comprehensive support and intervention. Universities have a critical role in promoting student mental health, but often struggle to provide adequate resources and support services.

Statement of the Problem

Student mental health is a growing concern, with increasing rates of stress, anxiety, emotions regulations difficulties and suicidal ideation among university students. Despite the critical need for support, many students struggle to cope with academic and social demands, leading to overwhelming stress and emotion regulation difficulties.

According to the World Health Organization (WHO) suicide is the second leading cause of death among 15-29 year old globally. With University students often falling within this age group. Specifically, the problems to be addressed; High levels of stress among university students, which can lead to severe mental health issues, including suicidal ideation, Emotion regulation difficulties, which can exacerbate stress and worsen mental health outcomes. Again, multiple reports of suicides involving students at Nigerian Universities, including the University of Abuja. Mental Health issues, academic pressures and economic challenges are common contributing factors.

In one instance, according to Sahara report, a University of Abuja student went missing and was later found dead in what was believed to be a case related to suicide. Also, a 300-level student of

Business Administration at Nnamdi Azikiwe University, Ebuka Joshua, committed suicide after taking a sniper. Stories have it that the deceased Ebuka Joshua, has been battling with depression the beginning of the semester following his inability to cope with his studies.

Sahara Reporters also reported that a young graduate identified as Ugwoke Jerry has committed suicide in Nsukka, Enugu State in October. It was learnt that Jerry was found hanged on a tree by his colleagues inside a forest in the community, a discovery which caused tension among the students. Before his death, the deceased had sent an emotional message to his mother. "You are the best mother ever, in this world. I'm sorry for disappointing you. Please." he said in the message to his mother. The reason for his action remained unknown.

He was lucky to graduate and had also completed his National Youths Service Corps. Some people are still in school finding how to graduate but he was even fortunate," a source lamented. Another student at Ebonyi State University committed suicide after failing a course multiple times, leading to severe depression.

The overall increase in suicide rates is also attributed to the country's harsh economic conditions and insufficient mental health support. This study aims to explore the influence of stress, emotion regulation, on suicidal ideation among students, informing strategies for support and intervention to promote student mental health and well-being.

Research Questions

This study aims to address the following research questions:

- i. What is the influence of stress, on suicidal ideation among students of University of Abuja?
- ii. What is the influence of Emotions Regulation on suicidal ideation among students of University of Abuja?
- iii. What is the gender difference on suicidal ideation among students of university of Abuja?
- iv. What is the joint influence of Stress and Emotion Regulation on suicidal ideation among students of University of Abuja?

Objectives of the Study

The main objective of this study is to investigate the influence of stress and emotion regulation on suicidal ideation among students of University of Abuja.

Specifically, the study aims to:

- i. Assess the influence of stress on students' suicidal ideation.
- ii. Examine the influence of emotions regulation on suicidal ideation
- iii. Explore the joint influence of stress and emotion regulation on suicidal ideation
- iv. Examine the gender difference of suicidal ideation among students.

Research Hypotheses:

- i. Stress will significantly influence suicidal ideation among university of Abuja undergraduate students.

- iii. Emotion regulation difficulties will significantly influence suicidal ideation among University of Abuja undergraduate Students.
- There will be a joint influence of Stress and Emotion regulation difficulties on suicidal ideation among undergraduate students of University of Abuja, Nigeria.
- iv. There will be a significant gender difference in suicidal ideation among undergraduate students of University of Abuja.

Empirical Literature Review

This section presents reviews of some of the studies conducted in the area of the current study under investigation. The review comes under: stress and suicidal ideation among students, emotions regulation and suicidal ideation, stress, emotion regulation difficulties and suicidal ideation.

Stress and Suicidal Ideation among Students

Psychological trauma often occurs when an individual faces an extensive degree of stress in which they are unable to cope with, resulting in difficulties processing and integrating the stressful event. Van der Kolk (2003). Definitions of trauma have been extended over the past few decades to include a wider range of traumatic experiences, including the sudden or unexpected death of a close other (e.g. suicide). Balliett and Newman (2009). More recent definitions of trauma have also evolved such that greater emphasis is placed on the individual's perceptions of the traumatic event as opposed to its objective features, giving rise to the notion that similar events can lead to grossly different outcomes across individuals. Balliett and Newman (2009). Despite high rates of exposure to trauma, only a small percentage of those exposed go on to develop clinically significant symptoms of post-traumatic stress disorder, achieving criteria for a full diagnosis. Balliett and Newman (2009). However, studies have demonstrated a connection between exposure to traumatic events and negative mental health outcomes, including depression, anxiety, substance use, and other externalizing disorders (Lilly et al., 2011).

While the act of suicide itself is often an independent act, suicide has the ability to affect broader social networks such as family, friends, and the community and can be experienced as traumatic. (Purdie et al., 2014; Murphy et al., 1999). Exposure to violent deaths, such as suicide, have been associated with grief and trauma, and traumatic events as such may create a greater risk for the development of post-traumatic stress disorder. (Walker R, 2014). Consideration has also been given to the impact of client suicide on providers such as mental health professionals. Pitman et al. (2014). A review of 57 studies revealed that the nature of the relationship between the departed and the surviving individual or individuals is associated with the adverse outcomes in the latter's mental and social health.

Robert (2008) saw suicidal ideation as a concept that includes all overt suicidal behaviours and communications such as suicide threats and expressions of wish to die. Furthermore, according to Shittu, et al., (2014) suicidal ideation is the thought about or an unusual preoccupation with suicide. A major concern among academic scholars about suicidal ideation has been to identify the prevailing factors that are associated with suicidal ideation. Thus, within the ambit of extant

academic literature, reveals that certain variables such as hopelessness, academic failure, depression, poor social support system, death of a loved one, emotional trauma, serious physical illness, aging, unemployment, financial problems, guilt feeling, dependence on alcohol or other drugs are associated with suicidal ideation (Hudgens, 2003). Among these variables, personality traits and academic stress have been found to significantly predict suicidal ideation, especially within the academic context (Zhang, 2012; Allred & Hogstromthe, 2013; Venumadhava & Mayuri, 2014; Shim & Jeong, 2018).

Emotions regulation and Suicidal Ideation

Globally, suicide is the second leading cause of death among those aged 10–24 years and a leading public health problem (Van, et al., 2020). A suicide generally includes suicidal thoughts, planning, attempt, and completion. Suicidal ideation precedes suicidal behavior. Suicidal ideation is the most significant predictor of suicide attempt and completion. Longitudinal studies have shown that the greater the severity (high intent or planning) and pervasiveness (high frequency or duration) of the suicidal ideation, the higher the likelihood such ideation is to eventuate in an attempt. Suicidal thoughts, defined as thoughts of harming or killing oneself actively or passively, commonly occur in adolescents and more so among female adolescents (WHO, 17 August 2014.). In low- and middle-income countries, such as China, the main risk factors for suicide among adolescents include the female sex, bullying and violence, mental disorders, fragile family dynamics, and peer relationships (McKinnon, et al., 2016).

Undergraduates (age of 10–19 years)—a unique formative period in which there are multiple physical, emotional, and social changes is a critical period for the development and maintenance of social and emotional habits (WHO, 17 November 2021). Promoting mental health and protection from adverse experiences and risk factors that may affect growth potential are essential aspects for physical and mental health in undergraduates and adulthood. Suicide is a complex and multidimensional process that is influenced by many environmental factors. Neuringer (1964) initially pointed out that cognitive classification is a factor that significantly increases suicidal thoughts and attempts. Recently, a review (Rutter, 2020) of many studies showed that the impairment of neurocognitive functions was linked to the risk of suicide among adolescents and adults. Accuracy rate was considered a measure of impulsivity or dis-inhibition when subjects reacted badly to non-targets (Greenberg & Waldman, 1993). Moreover, the concurrence of certain sources of acute stress, such as interpersonal conflict, may make adolescents more likely to act on their suicidal ideation (McGirr, et al., 2008).

Stress, Emotion Regulation Difficulties and Suicidal Ideation

Stress as an inescapable part of life generally touches a wide range of groups of population with no regard to their age, gender, educational status or socioeconomic status. Despite this fact, stress, depression and anxiety are prevailing mental health problems among college students (Kitzrow, 2003; Marthoenis, et al., & Sofyan, et al., 2018). College students undergo numerous educational, social, environmental and psychological adjustment difficulties in the new campus atmosphere which may affect their psychosocial well-being and learning outcomes. These happen because the

The new tertiary educational system has a big difference in its methods of teaching, academic requirements, type of relations between faculties and even relations among students themselves (Wabieh & Qaisy, 2012). In short, stress seems to be very common in college students' life because college students need to ensure their academic survival and prepare themselves for the further career. It is not a surprise that much of the academic stress at the college level is associated with what students learn and how they learn it.

Stress can be a healthy and adaptive people's response to the threat by mobilizing their energy towards the stressors (Khan, et al, 2015). Thus, it is important to note that a certain level of stress is essential for the students in a way that it motivates students to progress in their academic journey actively, would otherwise be inactive and uninterested creatures (Nandamuri & Ch, 2007). Many researchers have also noted that stress is not always negative. It also partakes positive motivational contribution in people's life. Take, for instance, exam stress or academic workload may motivate and strengthen a college student to successfully deal with his or her academic tasks and also enhances academic achievement and creativity (Auerbach & Gramling, 1998). However, if individuals fail to employ effective stress coping mechanisms to handle the stressful situation, their feeling of stress can persist over time and, in turn, become at a higher risk of developing severe physical and mental problems (Auerbach & Gramling, 1998).

Suicidal ideation is a common precursor to attempted suicide, adolescents are more likely to "develop" actual behavior in the presence of impulsive aggression. The findings of a recent study indicate an association between higher errors of commission on the visual sustained attention task and increase in suicidal ideation in mood disorder patients before controlling for depressive symptoms (Kim, et al., 2020). Moreover, errors of commission on the attention test reflect impulsivity and appear to influence suicidal ideation by interacting with depressive symptoms. Attentional bias task automatically recorded commission errors and the reaction time to the stimulus. Accuracy rate was considered a measure of impulsivity or disinhibition when subjects reacted badly to non-targets (Greenberg & Waldman, 1993). Moreover, the concurrence of certain sources of acute stress, such as interpersonal conflict, may make adolescents more likely to act on their suicidal ideation (McGirr, et al., 2008).

Negative emotional experiences may be more difficult to forget than neutral ones a phenomenon known as the "emotional memory effect." Emotional memory represents the storage of information regarding survival experience. Neurons provide emotional meaning to environmental stimuli through an association mechanism. Both negative and positive emotional memories leave traces in the brain and strongly influence how we perceive the world and ultimately guide decision-making behavior. Emotional memory affects emotional intensity and emotional health. The relationship between emotional memory and suicide has been an interesting topic in the field of suicide research. Emotional memory (Hamann, 2001) (also known as emotional arousal event memory) is a type of explicit memory that involves the process of encoding, storing, retrieving, and extracting emotional information under certain circumstances. Emotional information includes the subjective experience of emotional, physiological, and behavioral responses to emotion and emotional stimulation. Studies have reported that some adults who attempt suicide have low thresholds for distraction and emotional sensitivity when dealing with environmental cues and that reduced memory function may also be associated with inappropriate organizational strategies or problems in obtaining information during the initial coding process, leading to increased vulnerability to

suicide (Kim, et al 2020; Heeringen, 2002). Moreover, in the Cries of Pain model of suicide (Heeringen, 2002), frustration following a failed event leads to impaired emotional memory, and compared with neutral stimuli, emotional stimuli take longer to process, and emotional stimuli will direct more attention resources to the processing links of memory tasks (Plancher, et al., 2019), and bias in information processing is considered to be the basis for negative assessment of stressors and promotes negative memory schemas. This suggests the causal effect of specific negative emotional states on memory impairment. However, although most previous studies have focused on emotional memory, the impact of suicidal ideation on emotional memory is not yet fully understood.

METHOD

This chapter describes the research design, participants, data collection methods, and data analysis procedures used in this study to explore the influence of stress, emotion regulation, on suicidal ideation among university students.

Research Design

This study adopted a cross-sectional survey design. A cross-sectional survey design is one among the survey research methods that involves using different groups of people who differ in the variable of interest but share other characteristics, such as socioeconomic status, educational background and ethnicity. It is relevant to this study because the study is interested to examine the relationship between Stress, emotions regulations, and suicidal ideation among undergraduates.

Population, Sample Size and Sampling Techniques

The targeted population for this study comprises of both male and female first year undergraduate students from faculty of education University of Abuja, Nigeria. For effective and efficient research study, a random figure of 300 students from the population were randomly selected while the researcher employed the z score Formula to determine the sample from the population.

The Sample size of the study was 275 students. This was determined with online sample calculator (www.raosoft.com) based on the criteria of 95% confident interval, 50% response rate and 5% margin of error. With the following equation

$$x = z \left(\frac{c}{100} \right) 2r \left(100 - r \right) \text{ and}$$

$$n = N \times \left(\frac{c}{100} \right) \left(\frac{1}{E^2} + \frac{1}{x} \right)$$

Where N is the population size

r is the fraction of responses (50%) and

Z (c/100) is the critical value for the confidence level c(95%)

The sampling technique used in selecting the sample for the study was Stratified random sampling techniques. In the techniques the individual who participated in the survey served the representative of the population from which they were drawn. Sampling populations of 300 questionnaires was drawn using cluster and random sample method. The choice of random

Sampling was because it involves selecting a group of subjects (a sample) for study from a larger population). Each individual was chosen entirely by chance and each member of the population had an equal chance of being included in the sample.

The rationale for using the sampling technique was because the techniques ensured that the Law of Statistical Regularity which states that if on average, the sample chosen is a random one, the sample will have the same composition and characteristics as the universe (Kothari, 2018).

Methods of Data Collection

The instrument used for gathering the data for the study was self-developed questionnaires.

The questionnaire was designed in to three segments, Section A which deal with demographic status of the respondents while Section B, C, and D deals with the Stress, emotions regulations and suicidal ideation

Section A: The Perceived Stress Scale (PSS)

The Perceived Stress Scale was developed by Sheldon Cohen, et al (1983). It's a self-report questionnaire that measure how stressful a person finds their life to be. PSS is a widely used tool in psychology research and its considered the gold standard for measuring stress perception. It consist of 10 questions rated on 0 to 4 scale, and there are also shorter versions with 4 to 14 items. The PSS ask about how unpredictable, uncontrollable, and overwhelming a person feels their life is over the past month.

Section B: Emotion Regulation Questionnaire (ERQ)

This scale is commonly used to measure an individual's tendency to regulate emotions through two primary strategies: Cognitive reappraisal and Expressive suppression. This scale was developed by Gross & John (2003). It consist of 10 items divided into subscales: The cognitive reappraisal (6 items) made to measure the tendency to reinterpret a situation to alter its emotional impact to generate positive emotional outcomes. The Expressive Suppression (4 items) assesses the tendency to inhibit emotional expressions that lead to negative emotional outcomes. The ERQ rated on 7 point Likert scale, ranging from 1 (Strongly disagree) to 7 (Strongly agree). Higher scores on each subscale indicate a greater tendency to use that particular emotion regulation strategy. The ERQ has been adapted and validate across diverse cultural contexts, maintaining its reliability and validity. Also, previous studies in Nigeria had obtained acceptable internal consistency reliability for the emotion regulation questionnaire subscale (Chukwuorji, et al., 2020). Likewise, Chukwuemeka and Obi-Nwosu (2021) study yielded a Cronbach Alpha of 0.82 (cognitive reappraisal) and 0.77 (expressive suppression) for its applicability in Nigeria.

Section C: Suicidal Ideation Attributes Scale

This scale was developed by Bregje et al. (2014). It consist of five items each targeting an attribute of suicidal thoughts: Frequency, Controllability, Closeness to attempt, level of distress associated with the thought and on daily functioning. Responses are measured on a 10 point scale with higher scores indicating greater severity of suicide thoughts and associated impacts. The SIDAS (Suicidal Ideation Attributes Scale) is particularly useful for its brevity and its focus on

both the frequency and impact of suicidal thought. It has been validated across different population including community samples and individuals experiencing mental health issues. Studies has also shown that it has good reliability and validity. Making it a reliable tool for both Clinical and research settings.

Procedure

The researcher obtained a letter of introduction from the Department of Psychology, Nasarawa State University, Keffi. Thereafter, the researcher also obtained permission from the Faculty of Education, University of Abuja School of Management to use their students for data collection. Two research assistants was engaged to assist in the administration of the questionnaires. The retrieve questionnaires was captured for analysis.

Technique for Data Analysis

Simple percentage and descriptive statistics were used to analyzed the data collected. Simple percentage was used for demographic data of the respondents while the descriptive statistics of frequency and percentage tables were used to answer the research questions. Regression analysis was employed to examine the influence of stress, emotion regulation on suicidal ideation.

Justification of Methods

The survey involves the collection of relevant information from a representative sample of a given population to obtain their opinions or perception of the subject matter. In this study, the researcher was concerned with Stress, Emotions regulation and suicidal ideation. In addition, the researcher considers that the survey approach is best suited to provide insight on the experiences of the Undergraduates at the University of Abuja, Abuja Nigeria.

Ethical Considerations

- i. Voluntary informed consent were obtained from the student's base on assurance of confidentiality and research benefit of the study to them.
- ii. The research acknowledged the authors of every material used for the study.
- iii. The Participants were briefed on the study before administering the questionnaire to be completed.
- iv. It was not time consuming
- v. Research Assistants were trained on the protocols of administration of psychological instrument.
- vi. Confidentiality and anonymity were ensured.
- vii. Institutional approval was obtained from the Faculty of Education, university of Abuja through the Department of Psychology, Nasarawa State University.

RESULTS

This chapter presents the analysis and interpretations of the data collated in the field. The researcher used the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 27 for analysing the

The descriptive statistics used were frequency, percentages, means and standard deviations while the inferential statistics used for the test of hypotheses Multiple Linear Regression Analysis. Results of the analysis were presented in tables.

Demographic Variables

Table 1: Demographic Characteristics of Participants

Demographic Variables		Frequency	Percentage
Gender	Male	144	52.4
	Female	131	47.6
	Total	275	100%
Religion	Christianity	214	77.8
	Islam	61	22.2
	Total	275	100%
Marital status	Single	257	93.5
	Married	18	6.5
	Total	275	100%
Education Level	SSCE	106	38.5
	ND/NCE	169	61.5
	Total	275	100%

Table 1 shows the demographic characteristics of 275 undergraduate students of University of Abuja that participated in this study. Gender: Male (N= 144; 52.4%) and Female (N= 131; 47.6%). Religion: Christianity (N= 214; 77.8%) and Islam (N= 61; 22.2%). Marital status: single (N= 257; 93.5%) and married (N= 18; 6.5%). Education: SSCE (N= 106; 38.5%) and ND/NCE (N= 169; 61.5%).

Table 2: Pattern of Stress across Gender among Participants

Gander	Stress		Total
	Low	High	
	f(%)	f(%)	f(%)
Male	60(21.8)	84(30.5)	144(52.4)
Female	49(17.4)	82(29.8)	131(47.6)
Total	109(39.6)	166(60.4)	275(100)

Table 2 presents the pattern of stress across gender of the participants. Here it revealed that among males, 60 (21.8%) reported low stress, while 84 (30.5%) reported high stress. While among females, 49 (17.4%) reported low stress and 82 (29.8%) reported high stress pattern. Generally, majority of the students indicate high stress pattern meanwhile the male student tend to have higher stress pattern compared to the female students.

Table 3: Pattern of Emotion Regulation across Gender among Participants

Gender	Emotion Regulation		Total
	Low f(%)	High f(%)	
Male	76(27.6)	68(24.7)	144(52.4)
Female	58(21.1)	73(26.5)	131(47.6)
Total	134(48.7)	141(51.3)	275(100)

Table 3 presents the pattern of emotion regulation across gender of the participants. The results revealed that among males, 76 (26.6%) reported low emotion regulation, and 68 (24.7%) reported high emotion regulation pattern. While among females, 58 (21.1%) reported low emotion regulation pattern and 73 (26.5%) reported high emotion regulation pattern. Generally, female students indicate higher emotion regulation pattern compared to their male counterparts.

Table 4: Pattern of Suicidal Ideation across Gender among Participants

Gender	Suicidal Ideation			Total
	None f(%)	Passive f(%)	Active f(%)	
Male	9(3.3)	91(33.1)	44(16)	144(52.4)
Female	10(3.6)	82(29.8)	39(14.2)	131(47.6)
Total	19(6.9)	173(60.9)	83(30.2)	275(100)

Table 4 shows the pattern of suicidal ideation across gender of the participants. The results revealed that among males, 9(3.3%) indicate none suicidal ideation, 91(33.1%) indicates a passive pattern of suicidal ideation and 44(16%) reported active pattern of suicidal ideation. While among female participants, 10(3.6%) indicate none suicidal ideation, 82(29.8%) reported passive pattern of suicidal ideation and 39(14.2%) reported active pattern of suicidal ideation. Generally, majority of the participants indicates passive pattern of suicidal ideation meanwhile male participants were higher in both passive and active suicidal ideation compared to their female counterparts.

Test of Hypotheses

Hypothesis 1: Stress will significantly influence suicidal ideation among undergraduate students of University of Abuja. This hypothesis was tested using Linear Regression Analysis in table 5.

Table 5: Influence of Stress on Suicidal Ideation among Undergraduate Students of University of Abuja

Variables	B	t.	R	R ²	F	Sig.
(Constant)	3.203	17.495	.223	.050	14.345	.000
Stress	.231	3.787				.000

df= 1, 273

Table 5 shows the summary results of Linear Regression Analysis of the influence of stress on suicidal ideation of undergraduate students of University of Abuja. The results revealed that stress has a significant influence on suicidal ideation ($R = .231$; $F = 14.345$, $P < .05$) thus, accounted for about 5% variance for suicidal ideation among participants. Also, the results indicates a significant impact of stress ($\beta = .231$ $t = 3.787$, $p < .05$) on suicidal ideation with a positive indicator which suggest that increased in stress leads to relatively increased in suicidal ideation. In other words, this hypothesis was confirmed significant in this study. Thus, implies that the high level of stress experience by students is likely to lead to increased level of suicidal ideation.

Hypothesis 2: Emotion regulation will significantly influence suicidal ideation among undergraduate students of University of Abuja. This hypothesis was tested using Linear Regression Analysis in table 6.

Table 6: Influence of Emotion Regulation on Suicidal Ideation among Undergraduate Students of University of Abuja

Variables	B	T	R	R ²	F	Sig.
(Constant)	3.144	12.832	.182	.033	9.401	.002
Emotion regulation	.214	3.066				.002

df= 1, 273

Table 6 presents the summary results of Linear Regression Analysis of the influence of emotion regulation on suicidal ideation of undergraduate students of University of Abuja. The results revealed that emotion regulation difficulties has a significant influence on suicidal ideation ($R = .214$; $F = 9.401$, $P < .05$) thus, accounted for about 3.3% variance for suicidal ideation among participants. Also, the results indicates a significant impact of emotion regulation difficulties ($\beta = .214$ $t = 3.066$, $p < .05$) on suicidal ideation with a positive indicator which suggest that increased in emotion regulation difficulties leads to relatively increased in suicidal ideation. In other words, this hypothesis was confirmed significant in this study. Thus, implies that the high level of emotion regulation difficulties the likelihood of suicidal ideation among students.

Hypothesis 3: There will be a joint influence of stress and emotion regulation difficulty on suicidal ideation among undergraduate students of University of Abuja. This hypothesis was tested using Multiple Regression Analysis in table 7

Table 7: Summary Results of the Multiple Regression Analysis on Suicidal Ideation among Participants

Variables	B	t.	R	R ²	F
Stress	.238	3.978*	.294	.086	12.868*
Emotion regulation difficulty	.224	2.297*			

Sig. Level: * $P = .05$, (df=2, 272)

Table 7 show the summary results of the Multiple Regression Analysis, where the results revealed that stress and emotion regulation difficulty significantly and jointly influence student's suicidal ideation ($R = .294$; $F = 12.868$, $P < .05$) thus, accounted for about 8.6% variance for suicidal ideation among students of University of Abuja. Also, the results indicates a significantly independent impact of stress ($\beta = .238$ $t = 3.978$, $p < .05$) and emotion regulation difficulty ($\beta = .224$ $t = 2.297$, $p < .05$) on suicidal ideation among students of University of Abuja. See appendix II, for the histogram. This implies that, stress and emotion regulation difficulty has a positive relationship with suicidal ideation among students of University of Abuja.

Hypothesis 4: There will be a significant gender difference in suicidal ideation among undergraduate students of University of Abuja. This hypothesis was tested with independent sample t-test and the result is presented in table 8.

Table 8: Difference between Male and Female Student's Suicidal Ideation in University of Abuja

Gander	N	Mean	SD	t	df	P
Male	144	3.90	.375			
				.293	273	.770
Female	131	3.90	.369			

Table 8 presents the results of the independent samples t-test among students. The revealed the mean and standard deviation scores for suicidal ideation male ($M = 3.90$, $SD = .375$) and female ($M = 3.90$, $SD = .369$). The analysis revealed no statistically significant difference in suicidal ideation scores between male and female, $t(273) = 0.293$, $p = .770$. The results suggest that male students do not differ in their thought of suicide compare to the female students. In other words, the hypothesis was not confirmed in this study.

Discussion of Findings

The present study investigated the influence of Stress and Emotion Regulation on Suicidal ideation among undergraduate students of university of Abuja. Four hypotheses were tested.

The first hypothesis which stated that Stress will significantly influence suicidal ideation among undergraduate students of University of Abuja was confirmed as statistically significant; therefore, we concluded that stress significantly influence suicidal ideation among undergraduate students of University of Abuja. This findings is consistent with many previous studies. It is also consistent with findings of (Dyrbye et al., 2006) which suggested that chronic stress, when not effectively managed, can result in feelings of hopelessness, isolation, and the perception that suicide is a way to escape overwhelming pressures

The second Hypothesis Stated that Emotion regulation will significantly influence suicidal ideation among undergraduate students of University of Abuja. This hypothesis was confirmed to be statistically significant; therefore we concluded that emotion regulation difficulty significantly

influence suicidal ideation among undergraduate students of University of Abuja. This findings is consistent with previous studies

The third hypothesis stated that there will be a joint influence of stress and emotion regulation difficulty on suicidal ideation among undergraduate students of University of Abuja. This Hypothesis was confirmed to be statistically significant; therefore, we concluded that there is a significantly joint influence of stress and emotion regulation difficulty on suicidal ideation among undergraduate students of University of Abuja. This findings is consistent with previous studies

The Fourth Hypothesis stated that there will be a significant gender difference in suicidal ideation among undergraduate students of University of Abuja. This hypothesis was not confirmed to be statistically significant; thus, we concluded that there is no significant gender difference in suicidal ideation among undergraduate students of University of Abuja. This findings also consistent with previous findings.

Implications of the Study

The results of the study indicate that Stress, Emotion Regulation difficulties jointly and independently influence Suicidal ideation among undergraduate students of University of Abuja

Conclusion

In conclusion, it was concluded that Stress and Emotion Regulation have significant influence on suicidal ideation among young undergraduates.

Recommendations

School Authorities should do the following:

- i. Encourage open conversations about stress, emotions and suicidal ideation to reduce stigma and promote help-seeking behavior.
- ii. Provide access to mental health resources and Professionals, including counseling and therapy.
- iii. Educate students about healthy coping mechanisms and the dangers of avoidant coping strategies.
- iv. Foster a supportive campus environment that promotes social connections and reduces feeling of loneliness.
- v. Encourage undergraduates to practice effective emotional regulation strategies such as cognitive reappraisal and mindfulness.

References

- Balliett, N., & Newman, E. (2009). Friedman MJ, Keane TM, Resick PA (eds.). "Handbook of PTSD: Science and Practice". *Journal of Trauma & Dissociation*. 10 (2):222–223. doi:10.1080/15299730802607622. ISSN 1529-9732. S2CID 143277872.
- Greenberg, L. M. & Waldman, I. D. (1993). Developmental normative data on the test of variables of attention (T.O.V.A.). *J. Child Psychol. Psychiatry*. 34(6), 1019–1030. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1469-7610.1993.tb01105.x>.
- Hamann, S. (2001). Cognitive and neural mechanisms of emotional memory. *Trends Cogn. Sci*. 5, 394–400. [https://doi.org/10.1016/s1364-6613\(00\)01707-1](https://doi.org/10.1016/s1364-6613(00)01707-1).
- Heeringen, K. V. (2002). Understanding Suicidal Behaviour: The Suicidal Process Approach to Research, Treatment, and Prevention. *Jordan JR, McIntosh JL, eds. (2011-01-19). Grief After Suicide. doi:10.4324/9780203886045. ISBN 9780203886045.*
- Kim, S. I. & Kong, K. A. (2020). The relationship between performance of attention task and suicidal ideation in Korean patients with mood disorders. *Psychiatry Investigation*. 17, 374–381. <https://doi.org/10.30773/pi.2020.0020>
- Lilly, M.M, Valdez, C.E, & Graham-Bermann SA (August 2011). "The mediating effect of world assumptions on the relationship between trauma exposure and depression". *Journal of Interpersonal Violence*. 26 (12): 2499–516. doi:10.1177/0886260510383033. PMID 20829232. S2CID 45115155.
- McGirr, A. et al (2008). Impulsive-aggressive behaviours and completed suicide across the life cycle: A predisposition for younger age of suicide. *Psychol. Med*. 38, 407–417. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0033291707001419>.
- McKinnon, B., Gariépy, G., Sentenac, M. & Elgar, F. J. (2016). Adolescent suicidal behaviours in 32 low- and middle-income countries. *Bull. World Health Organ*. 94, 340-350F. <https://doi.org/10.2471/BLT.15.163295>, Pubmed:27147764
- Murphy, S.A, Braun. T., Tillery, L., Cain, K.C., Johnson, L.C, & Beaton, R.D. (1999). "PTSD among bereaved parents following the violent deaths of their 12- to 28-year-old children: a longitudinal prospective analysis". *Journal of Traumatic Stress*. 12 (2): 273–91. doi:10.1023/A:1024724425597. PMID 10378166. S2CID 40487268.
- Neuringer, C. R. (1964). Thinking in suicidal individuals. *Journal of Consultancy in Psychology*. 28, 5458. <https://doi.org/10.1037/h0045809>, Pubmed:14121178 (1964).

Pitman, A., Osborn, D., King, M., & Erlangsen, A. (June 2014). "Effects of suicide bereavement on mental health and suicide risk". *The Lancet. Psychiatry*. 1 (1): 86–94. doi:10.1016/S2215-0366(14)70224-X. PMID 26360405

Plancher, G. et al. (2019). Effect of negative emotional content on attentional maintenance in working memory. *Cogn. Emot.* 33(7), 1489–1496. <https://doi.org/10.1080/02699931.2018.1561420>.

Purdie N, Dudgeon P, & Walker R (2014). *Working together: Aboriginal and Torres Strait Islander mental health and wellbeing principles and practice. Commonwealth of Australia*. ISBN 978-1-74241-090-6.

Rutter, S. B. et al. (2020). Neurocognition and the suicidal process. *Curr. Top. Behav. Neurosci.* 46, 117153. https://doi.org/10.1007/7854_2020_162, Pubmed:32860213.

Van der Kolk B.A. (2003). *Psychological Trauma. American Psychiatric Publishing, Inc.*

Van Gerpen, S., Vik, T. & Soundy, T. J. (2020) Assessing adolescent suicide risk. *S D. Med.* 73, 82–86.

WHO (2021). Adolescent mental health. <https://www.who.int/news-room/factsheets/detail/adolescent-mental-health>. Accessed 17 November 2021.

WHO (2019). Preventing global suicide: a global imperative. https://www.who.int/mental_health/suicide-prevention/world_report_2019/en/.

[www.https://gmijp-edu.com](https://gmijp-edu.com)